

EVALUATION OF PHYSICOCHEMICAL CHARACTERISTICS OF SOILS AT AUTO MECHANIC WORKSHOPS IN BORI AND ENVIRONS, RIVERS STATE, NIGERIA

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Abstract

This study evaluated the physicochemical characteristics of soils at auto mechanic workshops in Bori and environs with a view to ascertaining their possible impact on the surrounding soils. Three auto mechanic workshops were identified as impacted sites with a control site where neither auto mechanic repairs, industrial nor profitable undertakings were selected for the study. Surface soils were sampled, prepared and analyzed following standard procedures. The pH values of the soils across the three auto mechanic workshops ranged from 4.84 to 5.23 with mean value of 5.01 ± 0.16 . The total organic carbon of the soils ranged from (%) 3.347-4.031 with mean value of 3.69 ± 0.27 . The total organic matter ranged from (%) 6.403 to 6.949 with mean value of 6.66 ± 0.22 . Total nitrogen contents ranged from (%) 0.186 to 0.202 with mean value of 0.19 ± 0.006 . Phosphorus content (mg/kg) ranged from 3.198 to 4.907 with mean value of 3.99 ± 0.70 . The electrical conductivity ($\mu\text{s}/\text{cm}$) of the soils ranged from 86.43 to 103.63 with mean of 94.32 ± 7.09 . The soil textural sorts revealed that the soils remained sandy loam. The results of the analysis revealed that the mean concentrations of the studied physicochemical parameters were all higher than that of the control sites except for phosphorus, %sand and %silt. This is an indication that the significant increase in concentrations of the physicochemical parameters is a direct consequence of the activities of the auto mechanic workshops.